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Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: SNHG14.

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Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We describe identification of SNHG14 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human embryonic stem cell.